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Evaluation of Teaching Practice Course According to The Opinions of Teaching Staff, Practice Teachers and Pre-Service Teachers*

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Abstract

The aim of this study is to evaluate the teaching practice course according to the views of the teaching staff, practice teachers and physical education teacher candidates who took the teaching practice course. As the program evaluation model, Stufflebeam's Context, Input, Process and Product Evaluation Model (CIPP) was used. Mixed research method, in which quantitative and qualitative research methods are used together, was used in the research. The quantitative data collection group of the research consists of physical education teacher candidates (n:63) who took the Teaching Practice course at Hatay Mustafa Kemal University Physical Education and Sports School in the 2021-2022 academic year. The qualitative data consisted of 7 instructors and 7 practice teachers who provided consultancy to the pre-service teachers participating in the study. The data collection tools of the research are the Teaching Practice Evaluation Questionnaire and Semi-Structured Interview Form developed by Aslan and Sağlam (2017). In the study, data were collected in two stages: In the first stage, quantitative data were collected and in the second stage, semi-structured interviews were conducted to explain the quantitative data in more detail. The SPSS package program was used in the analysis of the quantitative data obtained in the study, and the mean and standard deviation values for each item were included. In the analysis of qualitative data, descriptive analysis technique was used. As a result of the study, while there were some failing points in the context, input and process dimensions, the findings obtained in the product dimension indicated that the physical education teacher candidates considered the teaching practice to be effective at a sufficient level. When the data obtained from the interviews were examined, it was observed that all three stakeholders of the course made the same or similar statements on some issues, and while it was observed that their views were compatible with each other, the statements of the stakeholders were different from each other in some items. Depending on the results, suggestions can be made such as providing the necessary conditions in the practice schools, providing the necessary materials to the teacher candidates in order for the teaching practice to be efficient, and regularly giving the two-hour seminar courses given at the school by the practice instructors.

Keywords: Teaching Practice, Physical Education Teacher Candidate, Practice Teacher, Practice Instructor

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1. Introduction

1.1 Introduce the Problem

Teaching Practice course is a course designed to enable pre-service teachers to get to know teachers and students based on observations and interviews in schools where they practice. Upon completion of this course, students; will be able to learn about the organizational structure and management of the school, its operation, the classroom environment, the teaching of the lessons and the methods used. This course is one day a week for one semester. Among the responsibilities of teacher candidates; planning, examining a student, observing the lessons (Demirtaş & Güneş, 2004).

Teaching practice is a process that includes the activities carried out at the practice school in order to improve the skills gained during the undergraduate education of the pre-service teacher. In order for this process to function in accordance with its purpose, it is necessary for the relevant parties to fulfill their duties and responsibilities (Zehir-Topkaya, Yavuz, Erdem, 2008). Teacher candidates are required to experience a serious observation process during the internship period. However, internship periods in teacher training institutions in our country are passed in an extremely traditional and inefficient way, where the instructors and students are disconnected from each other and do not follow the developments in the world. Instructors should systematically observe teacher candidates and teacher candidates should systematically observe teachers at school. Good and Brophy (1994) stated that teachers could not perceive many events in the classroom. This is because the teachers are not well trained. Many teacher training programs have been insufficient in terms of teachers' ability to analyze classroom behaviors and specific teaching techniques (Selçuk, 2000).

Thanks to the cooperation between the practice school and teacher training institutions, pre-service teachers have the chance to gain their professional qualifications in teaching. Thus, teacher candidates can apply their professional and field knowledge efficiently. This process is of great importance in terms of ensuring a healthy communication and cooperation between the teaching staff assigned by teacher training institutions, the sharing of duties and responsibilities between the practice teacher in practice schools and the teacher candidate. This course, which consists of 2 hours of theoretical information given by the practical instructor and 6 hours of practice per week, is a joint study between schools affiliated to the Ministry of National Education and teacher training institutions. Achieving the high efficiency expected from school applications depends on the correct presentation of the mutual expectations of the parties involved in this process. In this context, in the theoretical part of the teaching practice, it would be appropriate for the practice instructor to determine the expectations of the prospective teachers and guide them. The support of practice teachers is the basis for the success of teacher training programs. The practice teacher is the closest educator to the teacher candidate. The application instructor is responsible for informing the candidates about the qualifications that are the most important part of the application process. In addition to the opportunity to observe the practice teacher while teaching, it also provides opportunities for teacher candidates to increase their own teaching experience. While performing their experiences, pre-service teachers see the classroom/field/gym/garden environment, they have the opportunity to make inferences from these experiences and to evaluate themselves. The practice experiences of the candidates should be observed by the teaching staff and practice teachers, and observation and evaluation forms should be used. After the application, the teacher candidates should be given feedback according to the information in these forms (Zehir-Topkaya, Yavuz, Erdem, 2008).

Since teaching is a profession of love, humanistic qualities should be sought in teacher candidates. Whether the student is prone to teaching should be determined by developing special assessment tools. Institutions that train teachers should train instructors in line with their needs. Instructors should set an example for teacher candidates by focusing on educational problems and protecting scientific ethics and human rights (Akçabol, 2005). A teacher is a person who has information about a program and its field. There is also a student group opposite. The teacher should not only give the necessary knowledge and skills to his students, but also influence the students with his character. The programs of teacher training institutions should be realistic, applicable and valid (Küçükahmet, et al., 2004).

The new concept that has appeared with the onset of information age affects both teaching and teachers as it does almost all domains. The present roles of the teachers are different from their roles in the past. Today, teachers are supposed to provide the information that is available but they are also required to have the ability to generate information and use it in a critical way. This new concept makes it essential that teaching and the education of teachers should be redesigned thoroughly. Turkish teacher education programs have a long history. With a long history that starts with the Ottoman Empire, our teacher education programs are to be redesigned in line with the new concept. As a matter of fact, it has been made clear in multiple studies that there are great many problems with the capabilities of the newly qualified teachers and the pre-service teacher education they receive in education faculties (Aslan & Sağlam, 2018).

1.2 Explore Importance of the Problem

It is the joint responsibility of teacher training institutions and schools affiliated with the Ministry of National Education to provide an implementation process that will contribute to revealing the subject area education and general teaching competencies of teacher candidates, whom we will give the responsibility of raising individuals who will shape our future. Based on this idea, it is aimed to evaluate the Teaching Practice course taken by the final year students of Hatay Mustafa Kemal University, Physical Education and Sports School, Department of Physical Education and Sports in the fall semester of the 2021-2022 academic year, according to the views of the teachers, teacher candidates and instructors in the practice schools.

State why the problem deserves new research. For basic research, the statement about importance might involve the need to resolve any inconsistency in results of past work and/or extend the reach of a theoretical formulation. For applied research, this might involve the need to solve a social problem or treat a psychological disorder. When research is driven by the desire to resolve controversial issues, all sides in the debate should be represented in balanced measure in the introduction. Avoid animosity and ad hominem arguments in presenting the controversy. Conclude the statement of the problem in the introduction with a brief but formal statement of the purpose of the research that summarizes the material preceding it. For literature reviews as well as theoretical and methodological articles, also clearly state the reasons that the reported content is important and how the article fits into the cumulative understanding of the field.

2. Method

2.1. Model of the Research

In the research, mixed research method was used to benefit from the advantages of quantitative and qualitative research methods. Mixed methods require combining or integrating qualitative and quantitative research and their data in a study (Creswell, 2013). In the study, Stufflebeam's Context Input Process and Product Evaluation Model was used as the program evaluation model, which provides the opportunity for comprehensive and systematic evaluation.

2.2. Statement of Research and Publication Ethics

In this study, ethics committee permission was obtained from Hatay Mustafa Kemal University Social and Human Sciences Scientific Research and Publication Ethics Committee with 13 meeting numbers and 03 decision number on 06.12.2021.

2.3. Research Population and Sample

The universe of the research consists of physical education teacher candidates who took the Teaching Practice course in the 2021-2022 academic fall semester, practice teachers working in schools affiliated to the Ministry of National Education and practice instructors. The sample of the study consisted of 4th grade students who took the teaching practice course at Hatay Mustafa Kemal University School of Physical Education and Sports, the practice teachers of these students and their advisors. Since there is no generalization concern in qualitative data, a working

group was formed during the data collection process. The teaching staff (n:7) and the practice teachers (n:7) were selected to make the study group suitable for maximum diversity sampling. The purpose of maximum diversity sampling is to create a relatively small sample and to reflect the diversity of individuals who may be a party to the problem studied in this sample at the maximum level (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2013).

2.4. Data Collection Tools

The data collection tools of the research are the Teaching Practice Evaluation Questionnaire and Semi-Structured Interview Form developed by Aslan and Sağlam (2017). The semi-structured interview form was prepared by the researcher as a secondary data collection tool used in the study. It is stated that the questionnaire has high reliability (Cr Alpha=.975). The most powerful feature of interviews used in qualitative research is that they provide an opportunity to obtain information about what we cannot see and to make alternative explanations about what we see (Glesne, 2013). In the development of the form, the literature on teaching practice was reviewed and the results obtained from the quantitative data were taken into account. Expert opinion on the draft form prepared in this direction was sought.

2.5. Data Collection and Analysis

In the study, data were collected in two stages: In the first stage, quantitative data were collected first, and in the second stage, semi-structured interviews were conducted with 7 practice teachers and 7 instructors in order to explain the quantitative data in more detail. The SPSS package program was used in the analysis of the quantitative data obtained in the study, and the mean and standard deviation values for each item were included. The following value ranges are based on the interpretation of the obtained arithmetic means: 1.00-1.80 = Strongly Disagree, 1.81-2.60 = Mostly Disagree, 2.61-3.40 = Moderately Agree, 3.41-4.20 = Mostly Agree, 4.21-5.00 = Strongly Agree. In the analysis of qualitative data, descriptive analysis technique was used. Direct quotations are included in order to ensure the validity and reliability of the qualitative data. In descriptive analysis, data is described, explained, interpreted according to predetermined themes, and some results are reached by establishing cause-effect relationships (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2013).

3. Results

While presenting the findings, firstly, quantitative data related to each dimension were included. After this, qualitative data that will explain the quantitative data are included.

Table 1: Demographic characteristics of teacher candidates constituting the quantitative sample of the study

		n	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	22	34.9
	Female	41	65.1
Age	20	2	3.2
	21	25	39.7
	22	16	25.4
	23	12	19.0
	24	4	6.3
	25	2	3.2
	27	1	1.6
	39	1	1.6
Practice Schools	Sports High School	8	12.7
	B.K. Anatolian High School	6	9.5
	E.B. Vocational and Technical A.H.S.	7	11.1
	H.Ö. Anatolian High School	9	14.3
	Y.S.M. Vocational and Technical A.H.S.	7	11.1
	P.R. Vocational and Technical A.H.S.	2	3.2

O. Middle School	9	14.3
A. Middle School	9	14.3
N. Middle School		
Total	63	100.0

Table 2: Descriptive values regarding the scores given by the teacher candidates to the items in the context dimension

Items	n	X	Ss
1. TPC is a must have course in all teacher education programs.	63	4.77	.58
2. TPC is a course that supports the theoretical courses in the field of teaching profession.	63	4.65	.69
3. TPC is a course that gives pre-service teachers the opportunity to apply what they have learned in the school environment.	63	4.85	.47
4. TPC is an important course for pre-service teachers to develop their skills related to the teaching-learning process.	63	4.87	.38
5. TPC has an important place in teacher training policy.	63	4.69	.63
6. It is the right choice to give TPC in the last year of teacher education..	63	3.31	1.38
7. The total time allocated for the TPC is sufficient to achieve the objectives of the course.	63	3.46	1.35
8. TPC has a solid philosophical foundation.	63	3.63	1.18
9. The roles and responsibilities of TPC's faculty and school cooperation stakeholders (school administration, responsible practice teacher, responsible lecturer, teacher candidate) are defined in detail.	63	3.93	1.24
10. The principles of conducting the teaching-learning process of the TPC are clearly defined.	63	3.92	1.22
11. There is sufficient explanation of the evaluation process of the TPC.	63	3.69	1.21
12. The skills (lesson planning, classroom management, etc.) intended to be developed in the TPC program are well balanced	63	4.07	.90
13. There are necessary conditions in practice schools for TPC to be effective.	63	3.20	1.34

(TPC: Teaching Practice Course, PT: Practice teacher, L: Lecturer)

In Table 2, the arithmetic mean of the physical education teacher candidates' views on the items related to the Context dimension varies between 3.20 and 4.85. The items on which physical education teacher candidates expressed the most negative opinion in terms of context, there are necessary conditions in practice schools for the 13- TPC to be effective ($X=3.20$ - Moderately Agree). Giving 6- TPC in the last year of teacher education is the right choice ($x=3.31$ - Moderately Agree). Physical education teacher candidates expressed opinions on the items other than these items at the level of Mostly Agree and Totally Agree. The opinions of the practice teachers and instructors regarding the survey data are as follows:

PT (n:1)/ L (n:1): I think that TPC does not have a very important place in teacher training policy. PT: TPC should not be given in the last year of teacher education. If today's education system focuses on learning by doing, I believe that the application of this course should be as important (n:2). L: The total time allocated for the TPC is not sufficient to achieve the objectives of the course (n:3). PT (n:2)/L (n:4): Necessary conditions are not very available in practice schools for TPC to be effective. Some of them have a hall, and some of them even have insufficient open spaces.

The items that physical education teacher candidates gave the most negative opinion in the questionnaire about teaching practice were related to the starting time of the practice, the total duration of the practice and the necessary conditions in the practice schools. It was observed that this situation was also observed in the qualitative data, and some of the practice teachers and instructors were of the opinion that the teaching practice should be extended over a longer period of time and the conditions in the practice schools were insufficient.

Table 3: Descriptive values regarding the scores given by the teacher candidates to the items in the input dimension

Items	n	X	Ss
1.The objectives/benefits of the TPC are clearly and comprehensibly defined.	63	4.19	.83
2.The aims/achievements of the TPC respond to the training needs of teacher candidates.	63	4.20	.74
3. The aims/benefits of the TPC are of a nature that can be translated into behavior.	63	4.20	.82
4.The content of the TPC has been prepared in accordance with the purposes.	63	3.98	1.12
5. The content of the TPC is sufficient to meet the needs of teacher candidates.	63	3.57	1.08
6. The activities to be carried out within the scope of the TPC are described in detail.	63	3.60	1.18
7.The activities planned in the TPC are consistent with the objectives of the course.	63	4.12	.97
8.In TPC, assessment and evaluation studies were determined in accordance with the objectives of the course.	63	3.98	1.25
9. The instructors conducting the TPC have the necessary qualifications.	63	4.04	1.24
10.TPC's practice teachers have the necessary qualifications.	63	4.26	1.00
11.The administrators of the schools selected for TPC have the features to support the process.	63	3.84	1.31
12.Pre-service teachers start the TPC with the necessary prior knowledge.	63	3.95	1.24
13.The number of pre-service teachers a teacher is responsible for is appropriate in the TPC.	63	4.28	1.00
14.The number of teacher candidates for which an instructor is responsible is appropriate in the TPC.	63	4.28	1.12
15.The conditions (physical, teaching staff, equipment, etc.) of the schools selected for the TPC meet the needs.	63	3.61	1.22
16.At the beginning of the TPC, the necessary material is given to the teacher candidates.	63	3.26	1.22
17.The information/explanations in the materials prepared for the TPC are sufficient.	63	3.50	1.35

In Table 3, the arithmetic mean of the physical education teacher candidates' views on the items in the Input dimension varies between 3.26 and 4.28. The item that physical education teacher candidates expressed the most negative opinion in this dimension, the necessary material is given to the teacher candidates at the beginning of 16-TPC ($X=3.26$ -Moderately Agree). The opinions of the practice teachers and instructors regarding the survey data are as follows:

PT: I don't think that prospective teachers have enough pre-knowledge to take the TPC (n: 1). L: I do not think that the outcomes of the TPC meet the training needs of teacher candidates (n:2). L: The content of the TPC does not meet the needs of pre-service teachers and the activities to be carried out within the scope of TPC are not defined in detail (n:6). L: In TPC, assessment and evaluation studies suitable for the purposes of the course were not determined (n:2). L: The administrators of the schools selected for TPC do not have the characteristics to support the process (n:4). L: The conditions of the schools selected for TPC do not meet the needs (n:4). L: At the beginning of the TPC, the necessary material is partially given to the pre-service teachers and these materials are not clear enough (n:4).

In the interviews with the instructors, the opinion that is common with the pre-service teachers in terms of input; It is related to the fact that the necessary materials are not given to the teacher candidates when starting the TPC or that there are not enough materials.

Table 4: Descriptive values regarding the scores given by the teacher candidates to the items in the process dimension

Items	n	X	Ss
1. In TPC, the activities of the course are carried out in line with the objectives.	63	4.15	1.06
2. In TPC, sufficient time is given to the activities of the course.	63	4.06	1.07
3. A two-hour seminar course is held regularly at TPP.	63	3.00	1.68

4. Pre-service teachers are informed about TPP (course objectives, activities, practice schools, etc.).	63	4.07	1.02
5. Pre-service teachers make regular observations in the classroom at TPP.	63	4.12	1.21
6. Pre-service teachers observe how the teacher conducts the lesson in TPP.	63	4.39	.97
7. Pre-service teachers observe how the mentor teachers manage the classroom in TPP.	63	4.38	1.03
8. Pre-service teachers observe what the practice teachers do during the day at TPP.	63	4.15	1.22
9. Pre-service teachers observe students inside and outside the classroom at TPP.	63	4.26	1.03
10. Pre-service teachers examine the curriculum of their fields at TPP.	63	4.28	.99
11. In TPP, teacher candidates examine the teaching materials used in their fields at school.	63	4.25	.93
12. Pre-service teachers examine the lesson plans prepared by the practice teachers at the TPP.	63	4.34	.91
13. Pre-service teachers prepare lesson plans at TPP.	63	4.07	1.16
14. Pre-service teachers examine the lesson plans they have prepared in TPP with the practice teachers.	63	3.92	1.15
15. Pre-service teachers examine the lesson plans they have prepared in TPP with the instructor.	63	3.74	1.28
16. Pre-service teachers regularly teach at TPP under the supervision of practice teachers.	63	4.25	.94
17. Pre-service teachers evaluate the lessons they teach at the TPP with the practice teachers.	63	4.20	.96
18. Pre-service teachers teach at TPP under the supervision of instructors.	63	3.55	1.53
19. Pre-service teachers evaluate the lessons they have studied at the TPP with the instructors.	63	3.71	1.33
20. Pre-service teachers work in collaboration with their groupmates at TPP.	63	4.42	.91
21. Pre-service teachers observe their groupmates while they are teaching at the TPP.	63	4.39	.90
22. Pre-service teachers evaluate the lessons they have studied at the TPC with their groupmates.	63	4.44	.91
23. Pre-service teachers use necessary instructional technologies while teaching at TPP.	63	3.92	1.19
24. Pre-service teachers use different teaching methods and techniques while teaching at TPP.	63	4.30	1.05
25. Pre-service teachers develop teaching materials for the courses they will teach at the TPP.	63	3.80	1.33
26. Pre-service teachers carry out studies (preparing exam questions, evaluating exam papers, etc.) aimed at measuring and evaluating students at TPP.	63	3.92	1.15
27. Practice teachers are constantly helping teacher candidates in TPP.	63	4.47	.75
28. Other teachers at the school attended for TPP also assist teacher candidates.	63	4.19	1.24
29. Instructors constantly assist teacher candidates in TPP.	63	4.15	1.20
30. School administrations assist teacher candidates in TPP.	63	4.00	1.19
31. Pre-service teachers communicate regularly with the responsible lecturers at TPP.	63	4.36	.98
32. Pre-service teachers communicate well with students studying at the practice school at TPP.	63	4.46	.83
33. Practice teachers are good models for teacher candidates in TPP.	63	4.25	1.10
34. Pre-service teachers are preparing a useful product file in TPP.	63	4.39	.99
35. In TPC, process and product evaluations are made in determining the success of teacher candidates.	63	4.15	1.19

(TPP: Teaching Practice Process)

In Table 4, the arithmetic mean of the physical education teacher candidates' views on the items in the Process dimension varies between 3.00 and 4.39. The item in which the physical education teacher candidates expressed

the most negative opinion on the process dimension was the item ($X=3.00$ - Moderately Agree) that two-hour seminar courses are held regularly at 3-TPP. The opinions of the practice teachers and instructors regarding the survey data are as follows:

PT: There are teacher candidates who stated that the two-hour seminar course is not held regularly in TPP (n:4). L: A two-hour seminar course is not held regularly in TPP (n:3). PT: Pre-service teachers do not participate much in the assessment and evaluation of students in TPP (n:4). L: Pre-service teachers do not carry out studies to measure and evaluate students in TPP (n:5). PT: Other teachers in the school do not help teacher candidates for the teaching practice course, and we do not see that school administrations help teacher candidates during the teaching practice process (n:4). L: In TPP, the activities of the course are carried out partially in line with the objectives and sufficient time is not given to the activities of the course (n:4). L: Pre-service teachers are not informed on time about TPP (n:3). L: Pre-service teachers teach under the supervision of practice teachers at TPP, and pre-service teachers do not evaluate their lessons with practice teachers (n:7). L: Pre-service teachers do not have the necessary teaching technologies while teaching during the teaching practice process and they have difficulties in developing teaching materials (n:4). L: At TPP, we cannot always help teacher candidates. Because there is no planning about this and the course density is too high. Accordingly, we cannot communicate regularly with pre-service teachers and practice teachers (n:7).

Considering the common features of these substances; While the practice teachers stated that they did their responsibilities in this process, the instructors stated that they could not.

Table 5: Descriptive values regarding the scores given by the teacher candidates to the items in the product dimension

Items	n	X	Ss
1. With the TPC, teacher candidates got to know their fields better.	63	4.66	.74
2. With the TPC, pre-service teachers understood the importance of their field better.	63	4.63	.82
3. With the TPC, teacher candidates got to know the curriculum(s) applied in the school more closely.	63	4.65	.72
4. Lesson plan preparation/lesson planning skills of teacher candidates improved with TPC.	63	4.63	.74
5. With TPC, pre-service teachers' ability to recognize students' individual differences improved.	63	4.68	.64
6. With TPC, pre-service teachers' skills in determining students' readiness improved.	63	4.55	.83
7. With TPC, pre-service teachers' ability to start the lesson more effectively improved.	63	4.57	.87
8. With TPC, pre-service teachers' ability to use different teaching methods and techniques effectively improved.	63	4.42	.92
9. With TPC, the skills of pre-service teachers to use instructional technologies while teaching have improved.	63	4.20	1.23
10. Classroom management skills of pre-service teachers improved with TPC.	63	4.58	.61
11. With TPC, teacher candidates' ability to use time efficiently while teaching/time management skills improved.	63	4.53	.77
12. With TPC, pre-service teachers' skills in solving problems that arise in the classroom have improved.	63	4.55	.73
13. With TPC, pre-service teachers' ability to measure and evaluate student achievement improved.	63	4.49	.83
14. With TPC, pre-service teachers' skills in preparing the materials to be used in the lesson improved.	63	4.38	.95
15. With TPC, the skills of pre-service teachers to communicate effectively with students while teaching the lesson improved.	63	4.60	.79
16. With TPC, the skills of pre-service teachers to ensure active participation of students while teaching the lesson have improved.	63	4.65	.62
17. With TPC, the pre-service teachers' ability to give effective feedback/corrections to students while teaching the lesson improved.	63	4.65	.59

18. With TPC, teacher candidates' ability to reinforce students while teaching the lesson improved.	63	4.58	.63
19. With TPC, the teacher candidates' ability to motivate students to the lesson improved while they were teaching the lesson.	63	4.65	.59
20. With TPC, the skills of pre-service teachers to use special teaching methods related to their fields have improved.	63	4.58	.63
21. With TPC, the pre-service teachers' skills of giving instructions/explanations to the students while teaching the lesson improved.	63	4.69	.58
22. TPC enabled pre-service teachers to develop more positive attitudes towards the teaching profession.	63	4.66	.59
23. TPC helped prospective teachers to get to know the teaching profession better.	63	4.88	.36

In Table 5, the average of the physical education teacher candidates' opinions on the items in the Product dimension varies between 4.20 and 4.88. The item 23-TPC, in which the physical education teacher candidates expressed the most positive opinion on this dimension, helped the teacher candidates to know the teaching profession better ($X=4.88$ - Totally Agree). Physical education teacher candidates expressed their views on these items at the level of Totally Agree. These findings show that the candidates consider the teaching practice to be effective at a sufficient level. The opinions of the practice teachers and instructors regarding the survey data are as follows: Most of the practice teachers and instructors expressed a completely positive opinion on the product dimension. *PT: With TPC, I think that pre-service teachers' skills in using instructional technologies while teaching, their ability to measure and evaluate student achievement, and the skills of pre-service teachers to prepare materials to be used in the course are not sufficiently developed (n: 1).*

4. Discussion

In this study, it was aimed to evaluate the teaching practice course based on Stufflebeam's Context, Input, Process and Product Evaluation Model (CIPP) according to the Views of the Teaching Staff, Practice Teachers and Teacher Candidates, and for this purpose, quantitative and qualitative data were collected. In the context dimension of the study; The arithmetic mean of the physical education teacher candidates' views on the items varies between 3.20 and 4.85. According to the opinions of the physical education teacher candidates in the context dimension, it has been determined that the necessary conditions are not provided in the practice schools for the efficiency of the TPC and it is not the right choice to give the TPC in the last year of teacher education. The opinions of the practice teachers and instructors in the qualitative data are; TPC does not have a very important place in teacher training policy, TPC should not be given in the last year of teacher education, if today's education system focuses on learning by doing, the application of this course should be as important as the total time allocated for the course. It is not enough for the realization of the program and the necessary conditions are not available in practice schools for the TPC to be effective. Some practice schools have gymnasiums, and in others, even open spaces are insufficient.

The items that physical education teacher candidates gave the most negative opinion in the questionnaire about teaching practice were related to the starting time of the practice, the total duration of the practice and the necessary conditions in the practice schools. It was observed that this situation was also observed in the qualitative data, and some of the practice teachers and instructors were of the opinion that the teaching practice should be extended over a longer period of time and the conditions in the practice schools were insufficient.

The arithmetic mean of the physical education teacher candidates' views on the items in the input dimension varies between 3.26 and 4.28. Pre-service physical education teachers thought that too many necessary materials were not provided at the beginning of the TPC. Considering the common view of practice teachers and instructors in qualitative data; They stated that pre-service teachers do not have enough pre-knowledge required for TPC and that the achievements of TPC do not meet their needs in educating prospective teachers. Considering only the views of the instructors in the input dimension; The content of the TPC does not meet the needs of teacher candidates and the activities to be carried out within the scope of TPC are not defined in detail, assessment and evaluation studies are not determined in accordance with the objectives of the course in the TPC, the administrators

of some schools selected for the TPC do not have the features to support the process and the conditions do not meet the needs because in some of them sports activities. While there is a living room, it is emphasized that even the garden is insufficient in some of them. In the interviews with the instructors, the opinion that is common with the pre-service teachers in terms of input; It is related to the fact that the necessary materials are not given to the teacher candidates when starting the TPC or that there are not enough materials.

The arithmetic mean of the physical education teacher candidates' views on the items in the process dimension varies between 3.00 and 4.39. Physical education teacher candidates moderately agreed with the item that a two-hour seminar course is held regularly in TPP in the process dimension. In the interviews with the practice teachers and instructors, the common view with the pre-service teachers; the two-hour seminar course is not held regularly in TPP. The common view of practice teachers and teaching staff is; It was found that pre-service teachers did not participate much in the studies on measuring and evaluating students in TPP and they did not carry out studies on assessment and evaluation of students in TPP.

Another issue that the instructors mostly focus on is; It was stated that they could not always help the teacher candidates in TPP. Because they complained that there was no planning for this lesson and that they could not follow the pre-service teachers due to the high intensity of the lesson. Accordingly, regular communication cannot be established with teacher candidates and practice teachers.

The average of the opinions of the physical education teacher candidates about the items in the product dimension varies between 4.20 and 4.88. Physical education teacher candidates expressed a completely positive opinion on the product dimension. These findings show that the candidates consider the teaching practice to be effective at a sufficient level. Practice teachers and instructors also expressed positive views on the product dimension.

Looking at other studies: Selvi et al. (2017) stated that teacher candidates generally need some knowledge and skills during School Experience and Teaching Practice. They stated that these deficiencies are often knowledge and skills related to pedagogical content knowledge and content/content knowledge. In addition, they emphasized that they had difficulties in School Experience and Teaching Practice courses due to their inadequacy in subjects such as current-scientific-technological developments/information, pedagogical knowledge, and professional experience, and that they were eager to make up for their deficiencies. When the perspectives on School Experience and Teaching Practice courses are examined; It has been determined that pre-service teachers emphasize more on the advantages of these courses. While interpreting the advantages of these courses, it is seen that they often emphasize advantages such as gaining professional experience and awareness, liking the profession / interest. Despite this, some pre-service teachers stated that they had disadvantages due to the insufficient place and time of these courses in the program. Considering the opinions they have about the effects of the courses they took in the faculty on the profession, most of the pre-service teachers mentioned the inadequacies of these courses, while few of them stated that the theoretical and applied courses were sufficient for them. According to Aslan and Sağlam (2017) it is observed that the duration that is allocated to teaching practice are inadequate, that schools are not determined appropriately and teaching practice should be implemented in schools having different conditions, that teachers and academicians did not have the necessary competencies, that appropriate materials about teaching practice are not given to teacher candidates, and that many problems experienced in the process of teaching practice, and that teaching practice did not effective to develop some important professional skills of teacher candidates.

As a result of their studies, Tüfekçi-Can and Baştürk (2018) revealed that novice teachers gained experience in many different subjects thanks to their teaching English in a real classroom environment. The study also revealed that prospective teachers' positive views on teaching practice, practice teachers, practice instructors, and evaluating their own performance outweigh their negative opinions. The result of the study revealed that the Ministry of National Education and the Departments of Foreign Languages in the Faculties of Education should share the responsibility of providing a good quality education to the novice teachers. Özdaş and Çakmak (2018) stated that the emphasis was mostly on "experience" and "observation-imitation" in the research. While negative metaphors for the "difficulties" category were produced from the metaphors obtained for the Teaching Practice Course, it was determined that the metaphors for the other categories were positive. Kılınç et al. (2018) states that the

phenomenon of teaching practice consists of four components, namely seeing the importance of classroom management strategies and knowing the material to be used, gaining experience in the teaching profession, first step in teaching, and satisfaction with the teaching profession. Pre-service teachers describe the teaching practice process as a process where they see the importance of classroom management strategies and the use of materials in the classroom, increasing the quality of classroom teaching and helping students learn. According to Aslan and Sağlam (2018) The time allotted for teaching practice is not enough, schools in which teaching practice was applied don't have appropriate conditions, partners of teaching practice don't have enough qualifications and the student teacher weren't provided enough information prior to the teaching practice process. For all that, teaching practice course has generally led to positive outcomes.

In the study of Kırçıçek and Yüksel (2019), it was stated that academicians stated that the practice school was beneficial in terms of many skills about its contribution to the teaching profession, and that they thought that the practice teacher contributed to the teaching contribution. Yücesoy-Özkan et al. (2019)'s research findings from the teaching staff of the teacher candidates; It reveals that they have professional expectations such as sharing knowledge and experience, guiding and directing, being a model, systematic and regular work, and personal expectations such as establishing positive communication, supporting and helping, being tolerant, listening and solving problems, and being easily accessible.

Topal and Uzoğlu (2020) stated that during the teaching practice process of primary school teacher candidates; they found that they encountered problems at 4 main points, namely the problems arising from the teachers in the schools, the school administrators, the students in the schools and the personnel working in the schools, and that these problems stemmed from the lack of coordination between the relevant institutions and the personnel organizing the process. In Batmaz and Ergen's (2020) research, faculty members and teachers stated that the Teaching Practice course contributed to teacher candidates in terms of carrying theory into practice, effective communication in school, developing positive professional attitudes, and experiencing the school and classroom environment; on the other hand, they stated that they encountered problems regarding the duration of the course and the use of educational technologies in the course.

Çevik and Müldür (2021) revealed three categories as positive experiences, problems and contributions as a result of the research. The results showed that the participants had positive experiences in preparing and implementing a lesson plan for reading skills, classroom management, communication between group members, and doing research. It has been seen that the problems are related to the process, model and negative emotions. It has been determined that the problems in the process are related to issues such as finding resources for reading activities, preparing lesson plans suitable for different classes. Cengiz (2021), within the scope of the study, showed that the observations made by the pre-service teachers in the classrooms enabled them to learn the characteristics of the students. In addition to these, pre-service teachers are pleased that the practice teachers give them responsibility, have information about the students, and share their experiences with them. Again, a pre-service teacher expressed an opinion that the expectations of the practice teacher and the practice instructor from the teacher candidates do not match. Perhaps the most striking point under this topic is that most of the pre-service teachers find the feedback given to them by the practice teacher insufficient. Pre-service teachers state that both observing and being observed enable them to see different perspectives. In addition, some pre-service teachers stated that observing their peers enabled them to see different methods and techniques and to obtain information about the field. In addition to these, most of the pre-service teachers stated that taking notes while observing their peers was helpful in keeping what was done at the end of the lesson in mind. All pre-service teachers stated that they saw the benefit of preparing a lesson plan during the teaching practice. The pre-service teachers stated that the lesson plans they prepared helped them prevent the disruptions in the classroom during the teaching process and guide them when they were stuck.

According to the participants in the study of Tonga and Tantekin-Erden (2021), some of the problems encountered in the Teaching Practice process are the disagreements between the pre-service teacher and the mentor teacher or the difficulties experienced in classroom management. When looking at the solution suggestions of the participants for these problems, suggestions such as keeping the pre-service teacher and the practice teacher in constant communication or using interesting methods to facilitate classroom management are included. In the part of the

responsibilities of individuals, it was mentioned that the practice instructors should be involved in the process as much as the teacher candidates and practice teachers.

4.1. Conclusion

In the light of the findings obtained; in the field of Physical Education and Sports, as in every field, there must be a strong communication between the practice school, the teacher candidate and the teaching staff triangle in order for the Teaching Practice courses to reach their goals in the teacher training programs. For this, it is recommended to benefit from the views of teacher candidates, instructors and practice school staff, and it is recommended that new configurations be made for these courses. Necessary precautions should be taken in order not to repeat the difficulties faced by pre-service teachers within the scope of Teaching Practice courses, in which they gain professional experience and gain opinions. In order to eliminate such negative approaches and difficulties, it is necessary to ensure very good coordination between the school and the faculty.

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